

INFORMATION ABOUT THE PROCESSES AND BASIC RULES FOR WORKING WITH PSYCHOTHERAPEUTIC PRODUCTS

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh, Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Azizaturemuratova85@gmail.com

Ibragimova Qundiz Tolibay qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University.

Utegenova Juldiz Maxmudovna

Student of Karakalpak State University.

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Abstract. *This thesis analyzes the conceptual content of information about the main processes of working with psychotherapeutic products, their clinical essence and role in applied psychology, psychological, ethical and organizational issues observed in their use, as well as the basic principles that must be observed when working with such tools. The research is devoted to the types of psychotherapeutic tools, the factors determining their effectiveness, and their compatibility with the psychological state of the user-subject.*

Keywords: *psychotherapeutic tool, emotional balance, autogenic training, sensory goods, psychological safety.*

PSIXOTERAPIVTIK TOVARLAR BILAN ISHLASH JARAYONLARI VA ASOSIY QOIDALARI HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tezisda psixoterapevtik tovarlar bilan ishlashning asosiy jarayonlari haqida ma'lumotlarning tushunchasi mazmuni, ularning klinik mohiyati va amaliy psixologiyadagi o'rni, ulardan foydalanishda kuzatiladigan psixologik, axloqiy va tashkiliy masalalar, shuningdek, bunday vositalar bilan ishlashda rioya etilishi lozim bo'lgan asosiy tamoyillar tahlil etilgan. Ushbu tadqiqot psixoterapevtik vositalarning turlari, ularning samaradorligini belgilovchi omillar hamda foydalanuvchi-subyektning psixologik holati bilan uyg'unligi masalalariga bag'ishlangan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *psixoterapevtik vosita, emotsional muvozanat, autogenik mashq, sensorli tovarlar, psixologik xavfsizlik.*

ИНФОРМАЦИЯ О ПРОЦЕССАХ И ОСНОВНЫХ ПРАВИЛАХ РАБОТЫ С ПСИХОТЕРАПЕВТИЧЕСКИМИ ПРОДУКТАМИ

Аннотация. *В данной работе анализируется концептуальное содержание информации об основных процессах работы с психотерапевтическими средствами, их клиническая сущность и роль в прикладной психологии, психологические, этические и*

организационные проблемы, наблюдаемые при их использовании, а также основные принципы, которые необходимо соблюдать при работе с такими средствами.

Исследование посвящено вопросам видов психотерапевтических средств, факторов, определяющих их эффективность, и совместимости с психологическим состоянием субъекта-пользователя.

Ключевые слова: *психотерапевтический инструмент, эмоциональное равновесие, аутогенная тренировка, сенсорные товары, психологическая безопасность.*

Introduction

The tools and products used in psychotherapy practice are a form of psychological assistance that directly or indirectly affects the human psyche, restoring emotional stability, strengthening internal balance, reducing psychosomatic symptoms, or enhancing individual reflection. Such tools are diverse, including audio recordings for autogenic exercises, aromatherapy tools, notebooks designed for self-analysis, mechanical tools for reducing stress, visual stimulants (colored lamps, hourglasses), sensory balls, technical devices, and other products. Working with psychotherapeutic products requires careful application, taking into account not only the technique of their use, but also the person's mental state. Therefore, professionals or users working in this field must work responsibly with each tool, following special rules. As a result, the patient develops a neurotic personality and is prone to hysteria, depression, and psychosomatic disorders. On the one hand, the person does not want to be dependent on others, and on the other hand, he wants others to recognize and support him. Of course, this is not always possible. As a result, these contradictory states create a feeling of constant dissatisfaction, that is, anger and resentment towards others engulf the person's inner world. At the same time, the person himself wants to be recognized by others as a kind, humane, and wonderful person. According to psychoanalysts, the failure to fulfill these desires is the impetus for the formation of a neurotic personality and subsequent depression. Over the years, every desire and desire that has settled in the subconscious and remained unrecognized gradually increases internal conflicts and leads to self-loathing. Therefore, they do not forgive themselves and resort to suicide. For such a person, severe stress or an unpleasant environment is enough to develop depression. Of course, here it is necessary to emphasize the importance of constant psycho-emotional stress.

One of the main rules that must be understood first of all when working with psychotherapeutic products is the principle of expediency and individuality. Each person has a different psychological state, temperament type, emotional sensitivity and reaction to stress, and one tool that has a positive effect on one person may cause the opposite in another - indifference

or an internal negative reaction. Therefore, any psychotherapeutic tool should be selected primarily based on psychological needs, and before using it, possible reactions should be assessed through individual psychotests, interviews and observation. According to the second important rule, the process of working with the tools should be carried out under professional supervision and consistent monitoring. In particular, when using visual or sensory stimulants, music therapy tools, meditation audio recordings or interactive stress relief devices, the emotional and physiological reactions of the person are observed. Their excessive effect, that is, excessive relaxation, emotional inertia or, conversely, internal restlessness, may occur.

Therefore, the principle of "one tool - one reaction observation" should be one of the main methodological approaches when working with psychotherapeutic products.

Another essential rule is the principle of psychological safety and ethical responsibility.

Psychotherapeutic products should be used with caution, especially when working with children, emotionally unstable individuals, those who have experienced trauma, or those struggling with mental illness. Since any product or tool can become a manipulative mechanism in relation to a person, the therapist or specialist must use each of them ethically and professionally. For example, it is necessary to anticipate the possibility of allergic reactions when using aromatherapy products, and psychodynamic awakenings in music therapy. In addition, the psychoaesthetic and design approach is also a factor determining the effectiveness of psychotherapeutic products. Any therapy tool has a significant visual and emotional impact on the human psyche. Therefore, factors such as color harmony, surface material, smell, sound, and light level trigger reactions at the subconscious level.

For example, blue balloons have a calming effect, while yellow light has an invigorating effect. In this regard, it is recommended to use the achievements of neuropsychology and modern psychodesign concepts.

Also, when working with psychotherapeutic products, the duration, frequency, and intensity of their use should be clearly defined. In order to avoid cases of excessive use, dependence, or sanctification, therapeutic tools should be considered as "auxiliary" and "supportive" tools, and it should be strictly ensured that they do not replace the main psychotherapeutic work. The task of a psychotherapist is to help the client understand the meaning of his life. One of the main areas that helps in the search for the meaning of life is faith.

Analyzing the works devoted to the psychological study of patients with hypertensive disease, we see an attempt to understand the relationship between the disease and the psyche. In particular, in some patients with a medical diagnosis, different manifestations of the reaction to the disease, recovery or exacerbation are observed. In this case, the role of psychological states in the occurrence, course and recovery of the disease is of great importance.

Accordingly, it is possible to increase the effectiveness of medical treatment only by psychotherapeutically influencing the patient's mental state. N. Pezeshkian shows the effectiveness of positive psychotherapeutic methods and approaches in the treatment of diseases caused by psychological factors. The use of psychotherapy in the field of hypertension requires a deep theoretical analysis of research on emotions in the field of psychology. Because psychological assistance is provided in the treatment of the disease, it must have a solid theoretical basis. Each study on the psychology of emotions is aimed at solving specific scientific problems and practical tasks, and is valuable in its own right.

In the modern psychotherapeutic approach, working with goods involves not only passively using them, but also forming a conscious emotional and cognitive attitude towards them. Therefore, the reflective model of working with psychotherapeutic goods is of particular importance.

According to this model, the therapeutic tool is brought into the conscious focus of the individual, a conversation is held about it, subjective perception is described, and associative experiences associated with it are discussed. Through this approach, a person objectifies his inner experiences, learns to understand and express his mental state. For example, when working with colored sand, modeling tools, or meditation cards, the level of spiritual awareness deepens and internal blockages are softened. In addition, methods of working with therapeutic goods based on an intermodal approach are becoming increasingly popular. In this case, psychic stimulation is carried out simultaneously through several sensory channels (visual, auditory, kinesthetic, olfactory). For example, therapeutic bulbs evoke a harmony of light and sound, or interactive aroma devices restore emotional balance by combining smell and sound.

CONCLUSION

Psychotherapeutic products are tools that directly or indirectly affect the human psyche, restore health, and restore emotional stability. Their use requires a high level of psychological knowledge, moral responsibility, an individualized approach, and the presence of control mechanisms. It should not be forgotten that each tool is not a tool, but a spiritual field that communicates with a person. When used effectively, psychotherapeutic products become a tool that serves not only emotional relief, but also conscious reflection, mental stability, and healthy personal growth.

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